

Green Synthesis of Fluorescent Carbon Nanodots from Rose Periwinkle (*Catharanthus Roseus*) for Biosensing Applications

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Abstract

In the emerging materials research for technology and applications, fluorescent carbon nanodots (FCNDs) are a new class of carbon nanomaterials and have demonstrated fascinating optical properties for bioimaging and biosensing applications. Here we report, a green synthesis of FCNDs using rose periwinkle (*Catharanthus roseus*) flowers which are plucked from the departmental garden. The as-prepared FCNDs are characterized by X-ray diffraction, transmission electron microscopy, Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy techniques. The fairly good fluorescent property of the prepared FCNDs is applied for biosensing applications. The calculated regression coefficient and limit of detection show that the prepared FCNDs are highly sensitive for biosensing applications.

Keywords: Carbon nanodots; Fluorescence property; Biosensing

References:

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